

AMAL JYOTHI
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING
K A N J I R A P P A L L Y

Accredited B Tech
Programmes in :

Accredited by

NAAC 'A' Grade (I Cycle)

'EXCELLENT'
band in (2021)

2- Teaching- Learning and Evaluation

2.6 Student Performance and Learning Outcome

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

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2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
1	2022	B.Tech Chemical Engineering	58 - 54	LINK
2	2022	B.Tech Civil Engineering	96 - 83	LINK
3	2022	B.Tech Computer Science & Engineering	131 - 113	LINK
4	2022	B.Tech Electrical & Electronics Engineering	34 - 30	LINK
5	2022	B.Tech Electronics & Communication Engineering	65 - 57	LINK
6	2022	B.Tech Information Technology	32 - 27	LINK
7	2022	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering	81 - 73	LINK
8	2022	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering(Automobile)	37 - 31	LINK
9	2022	B.Tech Metallurgical & Materials Engineering	22 - 22	LINK
10	2022	M.Tech Communication Engineering	2 - 2	LINK
11	2022	M.Tech Computer Aided Structural Engineering	16 - 16	LINK
12	2022	M.Tech Computer Science	5 - 5	LINK
13	2022	M.Tech ENERGY SYSTEMS	3 - 3	LINK
14	2022	M.Tech Environmental Engineering	10 - 10	LINK
15	2022	M.Tech Nano Technology	1 - 1	LINK

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
16	2022	M.Tech Struct Engg & Construction Management	24 - 24	LINK
17	2022	MCA INTEGRATED	56 - 56	LINK
18	2022	MCA REGULAR	16 - 16	LINK
19	2021	B.Tech Chemical Engineering	65 - 65	LINK
20	2021	B.Tech Civil Engineering	124 - 121	LINK
21	2021	B.Tech Computer Science & Engineering	125 - 123	LINK
22	2021	B.Tech Electrical & Electronics Engineering	45 - 44	LINK
23	2021	B.Tech Electronics & Communication Engineering	89 - 87	LINK
24	2021	B.Tech Information Technology	39 - 38	LINK
25	2021	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering	117 - 115	LINK
26	2021	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering(Automobile)	47 - 45	LINK
27	2021	B.Tech Metallurgical & Materials Engineering	16 - 15	LINK
28	2021	M.Tech Communication Engineering	1 - 1	LINK
29	2021	M.Tech Computer Aided Structural Engineering	5 - 5	LINK
30	2021	M.Tech Computer Science	4 - 4	LINK

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
31	2021	M.Tech Nano Technology	1 - 1	LINK
32	2021	M.Tech Struct Engg & Construction Management	15 - 15	LINK
33	2021	MCA INTEGRATED	57 - 57	LINK
34	2021	MCA REGULAR	61 - 61	LINK
35	2020	B.Tech Chemical Engineering	77 - 76	LINK
36	2020	B.Tech Civil Engineering	119 - 117	LINK
37	2020	B.Tech Computer Science & Engineering	122 - 120	LINK
38	2020	B.Tech Electrical & Electronics Engineering	42 - 42	LINK
39	2020	B.Tech Electronics & Communication Engineering	108 - 107	LINK
40	2020	B.Tech Information Technology	42 - 42	LINK
41	2020	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering	116 - 116	LINK
42	2020	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering(Automobile)	37 - 37	LINK
43	2020	B.Tech Metallurgical & Materials Engineering	17 - 17	LINK
44	2020	M.Tech Communication Engineering	2 - 2	LINK
45	2020	M.Tech Computer Aided Structural Engineering	8 - 8	LINK

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
46	2020	M.Tech Computer Science	5 - 5	LINK
47	2020	M.Tech ENERGY SYSTEMS	6 - 6	LINK
48	2020	M.Tech Machine Design	1 - 1	LINK
49	2020	M.Tech Nano Technology	2 - 2	LINK
50	2020	M.Tech Power Electronics & Power Systems	6 - 6	LINK
51	2020	M.Tech Struct Engg & Construction Management	28 - 28	LINK
52	2020	MCA INTEGRATED	50 - 50	LINK
53	2020	MCA REGULAR	42 - 42	LINK
54	2019	B.Tech Chemical Engineering	75 - 68	LINK
55	2019	B.Tech Civil Engineering	125 - 110	LINK
56	2019	B.Tech Computer Science & Engineering	114 - 86	LINK
57	2019	B.Tech Electrical & Electronics Engineering	33 - 25	LINK
58	2019	B.Tech Electronics & Communication Engineering	81 - 66	LINK
59	2019	B.Tech Information Technology	21 - 10	LINK
60	2019	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering	120 - 110	LINK

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
61	2019	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering(Automobile)	40 - 37	LINK
62	2019	B.Tech Metallurgical & Materials Engineering	25 - 21	LINK
63	2019	M.Tech Communication Engineering	7 - 7	LINK
64	2019	M.Tech Computer Aided Structural Engineering	15 - 15	LINK
65	2019	M.Tech Computer Science	8 - 8	LINK
66	2019	M.Tech Machine Design	3 - 3	LINK
67	2019	M.Tech Power Electronics & Power Systems	1 - 1	LINK
68	2019	M.Tech Struct Engg & Construction Management	20 - 20	LINK
69	2019	MCA INTEGRATED	49 - 49	LINK
70	2019	MCA LATERAL ENTRY	88 - 88	LINK
71	2019	MCA REGULAR	22 - 22	LINK
72	2018	B.Tech Chemical Engineering	59 - 58	LINK
73	2018	B.Tech Civil Engineering	121 - 121	LINK
74	2018	B.Tech Computer Science & Engineering	120 - 115	LINK
75	2018	B.Tech Electrical & Electronics Engineering	47 - 38	LINK

2.6.3. QnM - Pass percentage of the Students

No	Year	Programme	Number of students appeared - passed	LINK
76	2018	B.Tech Electronics & Communication Engineering	113 - 93	LINK
77	2018	B.Tech Information Technology	20 - 15	LINK
78	2018	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering	119 - 111	LINK
79	2018	B.Tech Mechanical Engineering(Automobile)	51 - 45	LINK
80	2018	B.Tech Metallurgical & Materials Engineering	26 - 25	LINK
81	2018	M.Tech Communication Engineering	5 - 5	LINK
82	2018	M.Tech Computer Aided Structural Engineering	11 - 11	LINK
83	2018	M.Tech Computer Science	8 - 8	LINK
84	2018	M.Tech ENERGY SYSTEMS	2 - 2	LINK
85	2018	M.Tech Machine Design	4 - 4	LINK
86	2018	M.Tech Nano Technology	2 - 2	LINK
87	2018	M.Tech Power Electronics & Power Systems	2 - 2	LINK
88	2018	M.Tech Struct Engg & Construction Management	21 - 21	LINK
89	2018	MCA LATERAL ENTRY	52 - 37	LINK
90	2018	MCA REGULAR	42 - 42	LINK